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AELIANA PINCENSIA.

Hadrianic *semisses* in the collection of the National Museum of Veliko Gradište

Abstract: This paper presents three previously unpublished Roman bronze coins belonging to the group of the so-called “coins of the mines” (*nummi metallorum*): Hadrianic *semisses* bearing the reverse legend AELIANA PINCENSIA, one of which is pierced, with a hook still attached. The three coins surfaced in the coin trade and are currently kept in the National Museum of Veliko Gradište. Despite the fact that the original find context of the coins remains unknown, the circumstances surrounding their acquisition by the museum suggest that they originate from the wider territory of the Roman mining district referenced on their reverses.¹

Keywords: *semis*, Hadrian, *nummi metallorum*, “coins of the mines”, *Aeliana Pincensia*, Veliko Gradište

Under Trajan (AD 98–117), Hadrian (AD 117–138) and Antoninus Pius (AD 138–161), peculiar small bronze coins in the denominations of the *semis* and *quadrans* bearing reference to various mining areas of the Danube and Balkan provinces of the Roman empire in their types and legends were struck. While the *semisses*, roughly of *denarius* size, were produced from brass (an alloy of copper and zinc) and therefore were golden in appearance at the time of striking, the smaller *quad-*

1 The authors would like to thank the director of the National Museum of Veliko Gradište, Dragan Bogičić, for granting them access to the coins and facilitating their publication. They are also grateful to Rista Miletić, the original owner of one of the pieces, for alerting them to the existence of these coins in the collection of the Veliko Gradište museum. Furthermore, the authors are indebted to Nenad Bačić who supplied the high-quality images used on Plate 1 ; image copyright rests with the National Museum of Veliko Gradište.

rantes were struck from red copper.² At least in part, these pieces – which have been attracting scholarly interest for generations – seem to have been produced not locally, but centrally: presumably at the mint of Rome.³ Apart from issues featuring the names and portraits of the three emperors mentioned, there is also a group of anonymous bronzes “of the mines” of the same denominations, displaying the heads or busts of gods and goddesses on their obverses.⁴ Johan van Heesch has convincingly demonstrated that this anonymous group – of considerable size – was issued under Antoninus Pius, whose mine coins with the imperial name and portrait are extremely rare.⁵

While Trajan had struck four different groups of *nummi metallorum* in different phases of his principate,⁶ just two issues were produced under his successor Hadrian. These two issues, each comprising *semisses* as well as *quadrantes*, were innovative, as compared to Trajan’s mine coins. Firstly, unlike the latter, which invariably show full-length female figures on the reverse, all the Hadrianic mine coins bear two- or three-line inscriptions in wreaths. Hence, Hadrian’s mint-masters adapted a traditional numismatic reverse type that had been in general use since Hellenistic times to the special class of the mine coinage.⁷ Secondly, both Hadrianic issues commemorate mining areas that had not featured under Trajan: mining ventures in the province of Noricum – MET(alla) NOR(ica)⁸ – as well as an area referred to as AELIANA PINCENSIA on the coins, which concerns us here in particular.

At first sight, it seems curious that this reverse, unlike the MET NOR coins, does not specify that we are dealing with a mining district. This omission is the reason why in early numismatic scholarship, the legend AELIANA PINCENSIA was taken to refer not to *metalla*, but to *certamina*: games in honour of Hadrian that were supposedly organised in Pincum, when the emperor visited Moesia Superior on his travels through the *imperium Romanum*.⁹ However, a quick look at the Trajanic evidence makes it clear that such an elliptic expression is not unparalleled among the *nummi metallorum*. While the majority of Trajanic specimens bear the word METALLI (followed by one or two explanatory adjectives) in the legend, the reverse of the earliest group is inscribed just DARDANICI:¹⁰ a legend that was to be revived later under Antoninus Pius.¹¹ The legend (*metalla*) AELIANA PINCENSIA may thus be presumed to have been phrased with the elliptic legend (*metalli*) DARDANICI in mind.

2 For recent metallurgical data on coins of the mines, see *RIC* II.3, p. 72.

3 For a general overview of this material, see Woytek 2004a and 2004b; for the hypothesis of production at the mint of Rome, see Woytek 2004a, 48–50. These issues normally display a markedly metropolitan style, like all the mainstream imperial issues of the period.

4 Woytek 2004a, 41–42, nos. VI–XIII.

5 See van Heesch 1979, 177–181. For coins of the mines with the portrait of Antoninus Pius, see Woytek 2004a, 41, no. V, as well as Woytek 2004b.

6 For a listing, see Woytek 2004a, 36–38, and Woytek 2010, 637 (table).

7 For the development of the type ‘inscription in wreath’ since the fourth century BC, for its occurrence especially on Hellenistic small bronzes and for some examples from the Early and High Principate, see Woytek 2019, 391–394, with figures 5–7, 15–19, 21, 30–31 and 38–40.

8 Woytek 2004a, 40, nos. I–II.

9 Morellius 1683, 118; Harduinus 1684, 405; Morellius 1695, 216f.

10 Woytek 2004a, 36f., nos. 1–2.

11 Woytek 2004a, 41, nos. V–VII; Woytek 2004b.

The precise extent of the *metalla Aeliana Pincensia* is not known,¹² but they clearly centred around the eponymous river Pincus and the settlement of Pincum, the present-day river Pek and the town of Veliko Gradište (Figure 1). In addition to the valley of the Pek, the *metalla* incorporated the valleys of the Mlava and lower Timok, all part of the tributary system of the Danube in eastern Serbia. The rivers are for the majority of their course not navigable, originating in the sparsely inhabited Homolje mountain region to the south, before descending through a number of gorges to the valley of the Danube in the north.

Figure 1. Core area of the *metalla Aeliana Pincensia* showing Roman period settlements and evidence of mining from the same period (after Mladenović in press, Figure 4).

Слика 1. Централна област рудног ареала *metalla Aeliana Pincensia* са римским насељима и троговима рударства из истог периода (према Младеновић у штампи, Слика 4).

The richness, variety and accessibility of ore deposits has resulted in this region being mined for metal from prehistory to modern times, mainly for copper, iron, pyrite, zinc, lead, gold and silver.¹³ Though later works routinely obliterated evidence of older ones, several mines show clear signs of having been used in the Roman period, including Zlot, Bor, Majdanpek, Kučajna, Rudna Glava, Tilva Roš, and Brodica.¹⁴ While the mines provided a variety of metals, the main importance of the region lay in its auriferous deposits. Gold was washed out from the auriferous sand of the Pek, its tributaries, and the Timok, as evidenced by large deposits of river gravel along the river banks, but also from placer deposits of the Pek and Brodica.¹⁵ On a much smaller scale gold was also mined from primary deposits, mainly auriferous quartz veins, as indicated by a number of mills for ore-grinding found in the area.¹⁶

12 Dušanić 1977, 76; Hirt 2010, 73; Mladenović in press.

13 For the geological and geomorphological characteristics of the region, see Jović 1997.

14 Dušanić 1977, 74–6.

15 Dušanić 1977, 74–6; Tomović 2000, n. 23.

16 Cf. Tomović 2000, n. 23.

Unfortunately, no systematic archaeological survey of the mining remains in the *Aeliana Pincensia* area has ever been carried out, and apart from the already mentioned sporadic finds and vague general references to remains of Roman gold washing dating from the early 20th century,¹⁷ no detailed general account of the Roman activity in the area can be provided.¹⁸ The most direct evidence for Roman works in the region comes from a few metallurgical sites. Fortified sites dominate this group, with furnaces and other evidence of ore smelting discovered within the fortification, as well as workshops for the production of metal tools, pottery, and glass.¹⁹ While most sites of the area that have been explored seem to be from late antiquity, in some cases coin finds indicate exploitation as early as the first century AD.

Ownership and administration of these mines is another point where our knowledge is limited. All of the silver-mining regions of Moesia Superior were imperial domains, as attested by the presence of imperial officials and moulded inscriptions on the lead ingots.²⁰ For the gold-mining areas of the Pek such explicit evidence of direct imperial control is lacking, but there are a number of other indications that these mines were owned by the emperor, too. The very existence of centrally issued coins with the legend *AELIANA PINCENSIA* strongly supports this assumption, with the adjective used to describe the mining region deriving directly from the emperor Hadrian's *nomen gentile*, indicating his personal property. Numerous finds of fetters in the valleys of the Pek and Timok²¹ would further support this interpretation, as the use of *damnati in metallum* was a practice restricted to first state-owned and later Imperial mines.²²

17 E.g. Wellisch 1917, 148.

18 For an overview of the archaeological evidence and an attempt of an assessment of the scale and output of Roman works in the area, see Mladenović in press.

19 The only site excavated on any significant scale is Krakul'lu Jordan, cf. Bartel, Kondić and Werner 1979; Werner 1985; Tomović 2000. On other sites investigated in the area, see Kondić 1982; Petković 2009.

20 Hirt 2010, 48–82.

21 See Dušanić 1980, 52 n. 357; Tomović 2000.

22 Millar 1984, 142; Hirt 2010, 97–98.

CATALOGUE

HADRIAN (AD 117–138)

Semis

Date: The *terminus post quem* for these coins is the assumption of the title *pater patriae* in AD 128;²³ in *RIC* II.3 a date of AD 128/129 is suggested.²⁴

Variety A (reverse legend in two lines)

1. Obv. [HADRIAN]VS – AVGVSTVS P P
Laureate head of Hadrian to the right.
Dotted border.
- Rev. AELIANA / PINCENSIA in two lines (central dot underneath the second A of AELIANA) within a wreath featuring two wreath ties at the bottom and a round medallion at the top.
Dotted border.
2.64g; axis 6h, maximum diameter 16mm.
Hole near 6–7h (seen from obv.), pierced from obv. side. An 8-shaped bronze hook (bent from one piece of metal) of c. 12.5mm length is attached.
National Museum Veliko Gradište, Inv. 1/2013.
Woytek 2004a, p. 40, type no. III (this variety: p. 67, no. III/2).
Van Heesch 1979, p. 193, type no. 15 (this variety: no. 320). *RIC* II.3, 998 (variety with reverse legend in three lines only). *RIC* II, Hadrian 1012 (erroneously catalogued as *quadrans*). *BMCRE* III, Hadrian 1853 (erroneously catalogued as *quadrans*; reverse legend in three lines).
Commentary: From the same reverse die as Lanz (Munich), auction sale 109 (27 May 2002), no. 449 (2.99g) = Peus (Frankfurt/Main) auction sale 372 (30 October 2002), no. 1213 (the specimen illustrated by Woytek 2004a, p. 67, no. III/2).

²³ Kienast, Eck and Heil 2017, 123.

²⁴ *RIC* II.3, pp. 20f., 48 and 143.

Variety B (reverse legend in three lines)

2. Obv. HAD[RIANVS] – AVGVSTVS P P
Laureate head of Hadrian to the right; one of the wreath ties on his right shoulder.
Dotted border.
- Rev. AELIANA / PINCEN/SIA in three lines (central dot above the C of PINCEN) within a wreath featuring a round medallion at the top.
Dotted border.
2.73g; axis 6h, maximum diameter 16.5mm.
Obv. struck off centre.
National Museum Veliko Gradište, Inv. 1/2013.²⁵
Woytek 2004a, p. 40, type no. III (this variety: p. 67, no. III/1).
Van Heesch 1979, p. 193, type no. 15 (this variety: nos. 318–319).
RIC II.3, 998. *RIC* II, Hadrian 1012 (erroneously catalogued as *quadrans*). *BMCRE* III, Hadrian 1853 (erroneously catalogued as *quadrans*; this variety).
Commentary: From the same obverse die as Gorny & Mosch (Munich), auction sale 118 (14 October 2002), no. 2461 (3.60g) = Lanz (Munich), auction sale 123 (30 May 2005), no. 586.
3. Obv. HADRIANVS – AVGVSTVS P P
Laureate head of Hadrian to the right; both wreath ties falling down his neck.
Dotted border.
- Rev. AELIANA / PINCEN/SIA in three lines (central dot above the C of PINCEN) within a wreath featuring a round medallion at the top.
Dotted border.
2.17g; axis 6h, maximum diameter 16mm.
National Museum Veliko Gradište, Inv. 880.
Woytek 2004a, p. 40, type no. III (this variety: p. 67, no. III/1).
Van Heesch 1979, p. 193, type no. 15 (this variety: nos. 318–319).
RIC II.3, 998. *RIC* II, Hadrian 1012 (erroneously catalogued as *quadrans*). *BMCRE* III, Hadrian 1853 (erroneously catalogued as *quadrans*; this variety).

²⁵ The reader should note that catalogue nos. 1 and 2 have been entered into the inventory books of the National Museum of Veliko Gradište under a single number.

DISCUSSION

The most interesting of the three AELIANA PINCENSIA *semisses* is **catalogue no. 1**, for two different reasons: firstly, because the variety with the reverse legend in two lines is much rarer than the variety with the legend in three lines, and secondly because this coin is pierced, with a hook still attached.

In general, only a tiny minority of the coins that have come down to us from the Roman period were holed in antiquity: surveys of a number of western European and northern Italian sites show that holed coins make up just between 0.3 and 0.6 % of the total of coins recovered there.²⁶ Among the pierced coins there are examples of all Roman denominations, but small bronzes – *semisses* or *quadrantes* – are decidedly the least common: in the previously mentioned surveys, these smallest denominations of the imperial currency account for only between 0 and 3.45% of all holed coins.²⁷ The reason for their rarity is easily explained. Usually coins were holed in order to affix them to another object, be it of wood, metal or cloth, or in order to wear them as jewellery, hung on a string or chain (*vel. sim.*), with or without a loop. Small bronzes were the least showy of all Roman coins, so it is easy to see why they were usually not selected to be displayed: gold or silver coins were much more suited for this purpose, and if one chose to display a bronze coin (or to wear it on a chain), it tended to be a larger one.

A review of some of the published holed small bronzes from archaeological excavations²⁸ provides a glimpse into the uses of such coins. In general, it has been observed that the purpose of coin perforation can differ not only depending on the denomination/metal, but also on the region;²⁹ still, across several geographical areas holed small bronzes seem to have been largely utilized in similar ways to larger denominations: mainly as jewellery elements – pendants – either alone or strung together with others. Apart from coins, such composite strings could contain both decorative elements (different beads, shells, animal teeth etc.) and pendants that clearly served as amulets (*bullae*, bells, lunates, miniature tools or *phalli*),³⁰ though often the two functions clearly overlapped. Thus we find a small bronze of Hadrian (perhaps another AELIANA PINCENSIA coin, although the photo available does not allow for a secure identification) next to a small silver bell on the chest of a child

26 Perassi 2011b, 271–275; Doyen 2013, Fig. 7.

27 Perassi 2011b, 271–275; Doyen 2013, xiv–xvii.

28 No empire-wide survey of holed small bronzes exists; coin assemblages that the authors have considered in this analysis include the following (unless a different source is cited, the data are taken from Doyen 2013, xiv–xvii): Viminacium – 4 *quadrantes* (Vojvoda and Mrdjić 2015, cat. nos. 469, 722; Vojvoda and Mrdjić 2017, cat. no. 2349; Vojvoda 2018, G 1749); Carnuntum – two *quadrantes*; Augusta Raurica:–5 *semisses*, 1 *quadrans*; Reims – 1 *semis*; Dalheim – 1 *semis*; Sogny-aux-Moulins – 1 *semis*; Alba Pompeia – 2 *quadrantes* (Spagnolo Garzoli 1997, 330: T31, 3, 4). Though the authors are certain that this is far from an exhaustive list, the inclusion of sites of different character and from different parts of the empire, including one local to the coins published here, leads them to believe the sample analysed should be reasonably representative of the phenomenon on the whole. A review of all holed small bronze coins found in archaeological context is beyond the scope of this paper.

29 Doyen 2013, xf.

30 E.g. at the necropoleis of Viminacium such composite strings containing coins have been found in the following graves: Vojvoda 2015, G 1426, G 2079, G 706, G 1339, G 1897, G 247, G 1775, G1 1111; Vojvoda 2018, G 1807, G 4288, G 342.

buried at Viminacium,³¹ likely forming a part of a *crepundia* style necklace, the jingling of which was intended to ward off evil spirits.³² At Alba Pompeia (Piedmont, Italy) a *quadrans* of Claudius and another unidentified small bronze were part of a necklace together with four turquoise faience melon-shaped beads placed in a *bus-tum* cremation pit alongside numerous other grave goods.³³ The richness of the burial offerings seems to indicate that, in this case at least, small bronzes were clearly not simply a poor person's substitute for more valuable coins, but were appreciated in their own right – the reddish gleam of the *quadrans*, for example, would have made an attractive contrast to the turquoise of the beads.

For some people at least, then, small bronze coins shared the appeal of their larger counterparts, both for their appearance and as objects that when rattled produced a clanging sound.³⁴ A possibility has also been raised that Roman perforated coins could at times have been viewed as amulets in their own right.³⁵ Such a case cannot be made for the small bronze coins surveyed in this paper. The generally poor preservation of these coins often makes them illegible today, leaving us unable to identify a pattern in their selection or assess any potential significance in the images they carried. While it is true that the materials that they consisted of were on occasion considered protective – e.g. bronze was meant to ward off bad spirits,³⁶ and copper was believed to have healing properties and prevent bad influences³⁷ – the authors feel it would be too far-fetched to speculate that the small bronzes were used for the inherent magical properties of their material. If there was an additional attraction to *quadrantes* and *semisses* compared with other coins, it was probably their affordability and small size, making them particularly suitable for fashioning children's jewellery and earrings, the two applications that we often find them attested in.

Returning to our discussion of the *semis* catalogue no. 1, it is very unusual to find an ancient coin with a loop or hook still attached, making this coin a very rare survival indeed. Examples in the numismatic trade from the provincial sphere currently to hand include a large bronze coin (diameter 30 mm) of the emperor Volusianus (AD 251–253) struck at Blaundus in Lydia, which was pierced and has a contemporary bronze loop attached (Figure 2), as well as a worn medallion (diameter 39 mm) with the portrait of Hadrian's favourite Antinous, struck at Smyrna in Ionia: most unusually, this piece has an iron loop tapped into its edge (Figure 3).

31 Vojvoda 2015, G 1708. The authors are grateful to Mirjana Vojvoda and Dragana Spasić-Đurić for providing them with the existing images of this coin; without direct inspection the secure identification of the type has, however, proven impossible.

32 Schmidt 1971, 18–21.

33 Spagnolo Garzoli 1997, 330: T 31, 3, 4; 332: 21. Other grave goods included a mirror, a bronze lantern, some *balsamaria*, two terracotta lamps, cosmetic containers and several other ceramic and bone objects.

34 Wunsch 1910, 462; Perassi 2011b, 286.

35 Perassi 2011a; Vojvoda 2015, esp. 54–56. The case of a perforated denarius of Hadrian with crescent moon and stars on the reverse is especially illustrative: it was found on a string together with two silver lunates, placed on the chest of the deceased (Vojvoda 2015, G 596, Više Grobalja necropolis).

36 Wunsch 1910, 464.

37 Plin. *Nat. Hist.* 34, 100–1378.

Figure 2. Lydia, Blaundus, Volusianus: *RPC IX*, 741. *SNG Aulock* part 8, 2932. Classical Numismatic Group, electronic auction 355 (15 July 2015), no. 278 (16.65 g, 6 h, max. diameter 30 mm). Photo © Classical Numismatic Group.

Слика 2. Лидија, Блаундус, Волусијан: *РПЦ IX*, 741. *SNG Aulock* део 8, 2932. Цласициал Нумисматиц Груп, електронска аукција 355 (15. јули 2015), бр. 278 (16.65 г, 6 х, макс. пречник 30 мм). Фото © Classical Numismatic Group.

Figure 3. Ionia, Smyrna, Antinous: *RPC III*, 1975. *Klose* 1987, 251, no. 11 (with plates 35–36), Classical Numismatic Group, auction sale Triton 8 (11 January 2005), no. 725 (37.52 g, 12 h, max. diameter 39 mm). Photo © Classical Numismatic Group.

Слика 3. Јонија, Смирна, Антиној: *РПЦ III*, 1975. Клозе 1987, 251, бр. 11 (уз табле 35–36), Classical Numismatic Group, аукција Тритон 8 (11. јануар 2005), бр. 725 (37.52 г, 12 х, макс. пречник 39 мм). Фото © Classical Numismatic Group.

Coins found during archaeological excavations are more likely to retain original fittings, but even in this context it is not an overly common occurrence, undoubtedly due to the coins having often been mounted using perishable materials. For example, out of 92 published perforated coins found during excavations of two necropoleis at Viminacium, only two had their original mounting preserved: an anonymous *quadrans* showing the helmeted head of Roma on the obverse and Aequitas on the reverse (legend: SC) was found on a hoop made of bronze (Figure 4),³⁸ while a denarius of Hadrian was still hanging on one made of silver.³⁹ Judging by the find position of the first coin in relation to the skeleton, and the loop diameter of the second (coming from a cremation burial), it is possible that both were worn as earrings.⁴⁰ We will return to the subject of metal fittings of bronze coins later in the discussion.

38 Vojvoda 2018, plate I, 1, grave no. G 1749; *RIC II*, Anonymous Quadrantes 12. The authors would like to thank Dragana Spasić-Đurić for supplying them with the photograph of the object used in this paper.

39 Vojvoda 2018, plate III, 3, grave no. G1 720.

40 It should be mentioned here that although loops of the design as the one featured in Figure 4 have been customarily identified as earrings, this has recently been disputed in principle, due to their impracticality, as the

Figure 4. Anonymous quadrans on a loop, from grave no. G 1749, Pećine necropolis (max. diameter 14 mm): *RIC* II, Anonymous Quadrantes 12.
Photo © National Museum of Požarevac.

Слика 4. Анонимни квадранс на алци, из гроба бр. Г 1749, некропола Пећине (макс. пречник новчића 14 мм): *РИЦ* II, Анонимус Квадрантес 12.
Фото © Народни музеј Пожаревац.

Choices made when piercing a coin can sometime be meaningful and warrant a consideration. While in some cases, like the piece in Figure 2, the hole was not made in the axis of either side of a coin, the situation is different in others. Sometimes coins were pierced – or loops were affixed – in a way that allowed displaying the design of one or both sides of a numismatic object in a special way: for example, the loop affixed to the medallion in Figure 3 at 12h enabled the wearer to display the portrait of Antinous in an upright position. In this context, it is interesting to note that the *AELIANA PINCENSIA semis* catalogue no. 1 was pierced through the neck of the emperor: if worn on a chain, Hadrian's portrait would have been upside down, while the reverse legend in two lines would have been perfectly horizontal, since the hole is placed directly above the inscription, in the axis of the coin. If the position of the *semis*' perforation was a result of design rather than accident, then it would seem that whoever pierced the coin wanted to display its reverse legend.

Such a choice would have been curious, bearing in mind low levels of estimated literacy for the middle Danubian provinces⁴¹ – even if the wearer knew the text's content, it is unlikely that many onlookers would have been able to appreciate it. It is, however, possible that the decision to display the reverse was not fuelled by a desire to exhibit text for the sake of what was written at all: in the aesthetic climate of the central Balkans ornamental decoration has often been given preference over figural.⁴² Empire-wide surveys, on the other hand, indicate that approximately half of all holed coins show no attention paid to the axis of the coin's iconography, with carelessness in placing the holes increasing with smaller denominations.⁴³ Furthermore, the vast majority of piercing interventions done on coins locally clearly ignore the image axes of both the obverse and the reverse;⁴⁴ the perforation and the resulting orientation of the *semis* catalogue no. 1 therefore may have been merely accidental.

completely closed hoops could not be easily taken off; cf. Milovanović 2007, type IVa–a1. Pendants on headgear or temple rings could provide an alternative identification.

41 Wilkes 2005, 180 and n. 151.

42 Cf. Mladenović 2016. One can in fact find several other examples among holed coins recovered from the necropoleis of Viminacium where piercing seems to favour the non-figural side of the coin, if the coin was to be worn suspended, cf. Vojvoda 2015, G 596, G1426 and G2049.

43 Perassi 2011, 278–284.

44 Cf. Vojvoda 2015; Vojvoda 2018.

The most immediate comparandum to the pierced AELIANA PINCENSIA *semis* with a loop published here is an object from the antiquities trade encompassing not one, but two bronze specimens of the group of the “coins of the mines”. It is a piece of twisted bronze wire on which two pierced bronze coins are suspended, both of the anonymous METAL DELM issue (Figure 5): one *semis* (obv. helmeted head of Mars, rev. cuirass⁴⁵) and one *quadrans* (obv. bust of Diana, rev. stag⁴⁶). Since the authors did not have the opportunity to personally inspect this piece, but know it just from the publication in the auction catalogue, the possibility that it is a modern fabrication cannot be completely excluded. However, to judge from the digital images available, this looks like an ancient product, and the patination of all three parts of the object is in keeping with this hypothesis.

Figure 5. Two METAL DELM bronze coins on a bronze hoop. The coins are: Woytek 2004a, no. XII (diameter 19 mm) and no. XIII (diameter 14 mm). Gerhard Hirsch Nachfolger (Munich), auction sale 303 (25 September 2014), no. 3046 (no weight of the object given). Photo © Gerhard Hirsch Nachf.

Слика 5. Два METAL DELM бронзана новчића на бронзаној алци. Новчићи су: Woytek 2004a, бр. XII (пречник 19 мм) и бр. XIII (пречник 14 мм). Gerhard Hirsch Nachfolger (Минхен), аукцијска продаја 303 (25. септембар 2014), бр. 3046 (тежина предмета није наведена). Фото © Gerhard Hirsch Nachf.

The design of the copper alloy wire with overlapping wrapped ends is characteristic of locally produced jewellery in the Central Balkans. Between the first and the fourth century AD bracelets, earrings and finger rings were all produced in the same form, differing only in size.⁴⁷ The object from the trade in Figure 5 has an estimated girth of 11–12cm (diameter c. 3.5cm). Hoops of this design bearing a single pendant have routinely been characterised as earrings, and the anonymous *quadrans* illustrated in Figure 4 that is suspended on a loop of identical design has in fact been found on a skeleton in such a position that would indicate it serving precisely that purpose. The hoop in Figure 4, as well as known earring hoops of similar design were however of a smaller diameter than the loop from the trade,⁴⁸ making it unlikely that the object in Figure 5 (featuring not one, but two coins) served as an earring. Since it would have fitted a wrist of a very young child (newborn to around 2 years old), it might perhaps have been a child’s bracelet.⁴⁹ The second viable option is that the item is an oversized loop used to suspend coins on a now missing object. Hoops of the same construction and diameter, but executed in precious metal, have been recorded in the region and were used to hang pendants on bracelets, tor-

45 Woytek 2004a, 42, no. XII. *RIC* II, Hadrian 1014 (erroneously listed as a *quadrans*).

46 Woytek 2004a, 42, no. XIII. *RIC* II, Hadrian 1013 (rev. erroneously described as a “goat”).

47 For a discussion and further bibliography, see Milovanović 2007, 25.

48 Milovanović 2007, cat. nos. 185–207.

49 For an example of another bracelet of this design found locally, see Zotović and Jordović 1990: G1-35: 4.

ques or diadems.⁵⁰ Without knowing if we are seeing the object in its entirety, or if it had been part of a larger whole, its identification as either a bracelet or a pendant remains speculative.

One of the key tasks in current research on the coins of the mines is gathering find data, from which we can learn more about the circulation patterns of *nummi metallorum*. As has been mentioned above, they followed the imperial denominational system and could therefore circulate wherever bronze coins of this system were accepted; however, it seems that they were primarily used in the areas mentioned on their reverses, so that they occupy a peculiar middle position between imperial and provincial coins. In more recent times, four DARDANICI bronze coins that had been discovered in Sočanica became known,⁵¹ and one Trajanic mine quadrans (METALLI VLPIANI DELM) discovered in excavations at the Belgrade (Singidunum) fortress in 1981 was published by Sonja Stamenković.⁵² The authors of the present paper published five anonymous METAL DELM *quadrantes* from the collection of Petar Fajfrić, which were all found at the site Duge Njive, on the territory of the village Banovo Polje (commune of Bogatić) in western Serbia; these coins are deposited at the National Museum of Šabac.⁵³ A few years later four more *nummi metallorum* were discovered at the same site of Duge Njive, two METAL DELM and two METAL AVRELIANIS specimens.⁵⁴ The lion's share of the coins of the mines that turn up are, however, sadly unprovenanced, because they surface in the numismatic trade.⁵⁵

Provenance information for the Hadrianic AELIANA PINCENSIA issue has been very meagre so far. In 1977 Simić and Vasić published two *semisses* of this group from the collection of the National Museum in Belgrade and the Weifert collection.⁵⁶ However, their claim that “toutes les pièces de ces collections ont été trouvées sur le territoire du Mont Kosmaj, plus précisément dans les alentours des villages de Baba e Guberevac, célèbres par leurs mines de plomb et d'argent”⁵⁷ is misleading. While this may indeed be the findspot of the specimen in the National Museum collection, the coin from the Weifert collection is not provenanced. It is true that “more than 80%” of the ancient coins of this collection were found on Yugoslav territory (in the borders of 1918–1929), as we read in the introduction to the catalogue of the Weifert collection, published in Vienna in 1929;⁵⁸ however, local coin finds were not the only source for this magnificent collection, and there is no specific provenance information for Weifert's AELIANA PINCENSIA specimen.⁵⁹

50 E.g. Popović and Borić-Brešković 1994, cat. no. 6, Pl. VI and VII.

51 Woytek 2004b, 138, with reference to Peja 2000 (two specimens of the Trajanic and two of the anonymous series).

52 Stamenković 2010, 243f.

53 Mladenović and Woytek 2012, 12–16.

54 Vojvoda and Petrović 2016.

55 For the recent publication of an AELIANA PINCENSIA coin, see Woytek 2020; however, we do not know where this group of coins was found.

56 Simić and Vasić 1977, 58, nos. 22–23.

57 Simić and Vasić 1977, 49.

58 Elmer 1929, p. IV.

59 Elmer 1929, 50, no. 843. The indication by Simić and Vasić 1977, 58, no. 23 (“W[eifert]. n. inv. 847”) needs to be corrected.

Despite the fact that the three AELIANA PINCENSIA coins published here were not discovered in a secure archaeological context, what is known about the biography of these objects prior to entering the collection of the National Museum of Veliko Gradište may provide some support to the theory that the coins were originally found in the wider area of the *metalla* referred to on their reverses. All three coins in our catalogue were purchased at official coin fairs regularly organised by the Serbian Numismatic Society. **Catalogue nos. 1 and 2** were bought together by the Museum in 2013, **catalogue no. 3** was bought 10 years earlier by Mr Rista Miletić and gifted to the Museum upon its founding.⁶⁰ At the fair the coins were purchased from ‘wholesalers’ from the vicinity of Požarevac, who visit local villages in the wider hinterland of Viminacium, the lower Mlava and the Pek area buying up any chance finds from the local population, uncleaned and for a pittance. **Catalogue nos. 1 and 2** were in a bag of around 500 coins collected that way; these two were sold off separately as after cleaning it became apparent that they have individual value, while the rest of the coins from the bag were sold in bulk. Though without a secure find spot, we feel that the circumstances of the coins’ purchase make it appear likely that the specimens published here were originally found in the wider area of the *metalla* AELIANA PINCENSIA. If this is indeed the case, the new data would add significantly to the currently meagre body of evidence relating to the circulation of these *nummi metallorum*.

60 The authors would like to once more express their gratitude to Dragan Bogičić and Rista Miletić for candidly sharing details of their purchases with them.

ABBREVIATIONS

- BMCRE* III H. Mattingly, *Coins of the Roman Empire in the British Museum, vol. 3: Nerva to Hadrian*. London 1936.
- RIC* II H. Mattingly and E. A. Sydenham, *The Roman Imperial Coinage, vol. 2: Vespasian to Hadrian*. London 1926 (reprinted 1989).
- RIC* II.3 R. A. Abdy and P. F. Mittag, *The Roman Imperial Coinage, vol. 2, part 3: From AD 117–138. Hadrian*. London 2019.
- RPC* III M. Amandry and A. Burnett, *Roman Provincial Coinage, vol. 3: Nerva, Trajan and Hadrian (AD 96–138)*. London – Paris 2015.
- RPC* IX A. Hostein and J. Mairat (commenced by E. Levante), *Roman Provincial Coinage, vol. 9: From Trajan Decius to Uranius Antoninus (AD 249–254)*. London – Paris 2016.
- SNG Aulock* *Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum. Deutschland. Sammlung v. Aulock*. 18 parts. Berlin 1957–1968.

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AELIANA PINCENSIA.
СЕМИСИ ХАДРИЈАНОВОГ ПЕРИОДА ИЗ КОЛЕКЦИЈЕ НАРОДНОГ
МУЗЕЈА ВЕЛИКО ГРАДИШТЕ

РЕЗИМЕ

У овом раду презентујемо три до сада непубликована римска новчића *nummi metallorum* типа- семисе са легендом AELIANA PINCENSIA из доба Хадријанове владавине; један од новчића је перфориран, са очуваном алком. Новчићи су део нумизматичке збирке Народног музеја у Великом Градишту, за чију збирку су откупљени на нумизматичком тржишту. Упркос чињеници да је оригинални контекст налаза овог новца непознат, околности под којима је набављен сугеришу да је највероватније нађен на територији римског рударског округа који је посведочен на њиховом реверсу.

Кључне речи: семис, Хадријан, *nummi metallorum*, руднички новац, *Aeliana Pincensia*, Велико Градиште

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